

BACTERIAL DIVERSITY OF FRESHWATER LAKE MATS OF THE ARGENTINE ISLANDS OF THE MARINE ANTARCTICA

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Microbial mats that develop in Antarctic lakes are unique and highly diverse habitats in which microorganisms encounter extreme living conditions, which has led to the emergence of new biochemical adaptations. Bacterial mats ensure the maintenance of complex ecological relationships due to the ability of microorganisms in their composition to synthesize and secrete allelopathic substances that suppress the growth of competitors, contributing to the stability of communities. Such processes are key to the formation and maintenance of ecosystem stability, especially under conditions of limited resources. Finding the diversity of microorganisms in bacterial mats of freshwater lakes is aimed at deepening the understanding of the processes of functioning of microbial communities in extreme conditions and the possibilities of their use in biotechnological processes. Strains of microorganisms of various ecological-trophic groups isolated from microbial mats of Antarctic lakes are of important practical importance: they synthesize antimicrobial substances, exopolysaccharides and other biologically active substances, and have the ability to break down various high-molecular compounds.

The object of research was freshwater lakes on the islands of Irizar and Uruguay (Argentine Islands, maritime Antarctica). The diversity of microorganisms of bacterial mats of freshwater lakes was determined in samples taken on the islands of Irizar and Uruguay during the 28th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition (2023–2024). Metagenomic DNA was isolated from the samples, and V3-V4 amplicons of the variable region of the 16S rRNA gene were sequenced using 341F (5-CCTAYGGGRBGCASCAG-3) and 806R (5-GGACTACNNGGGTATCTAAT-3) primers. Amplification was performed using Q5 DNA polymerase (NEB, USA) on an Eppendorf MasterCycler gradient thermal cycler (Eppendorf, Germany). The amplicons were sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq device as a paired ends library (2 × 250 nucleotides) with a sequencing depth of 100,000 reads from each end (Novogene Europe, Germany). Barcode and adapter sequences were removed using the cutadapt version 3.3 program and merged using the flash version 1.2.11 program. Sequence clustering with respect to operational taxonomic units was performed using uparse version 7 and taxonomic annotation was performed using qiime version 1.9.1.

Bacterial diversity at different taxonomic levels did not differ significantly between samples. For samples collected from a freshwater lake on Irizar and Uruguay islands, 107 and 121 units were identified at the genus level, and 30 and 28 at the species level, respectively. However, the samples differed significantly in the taxonomic distribution of microorganisms. Thus, in samples collected on Irizar Island, cyanobacteria of the genera *Tychonema* and *Leptolyngbya* dominated. Representatives of the genus *Tychonema* in samples collected on Uruguay Island accounted for only 0.08–0.35%. In the analyzed samples of bacterial mats of a freshwater lake on Uruguay Island, bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* dominated – 10–19% depending on the time of sample collection. As a result of comparing the distribution of OTUs between samples, it was found that there are also certain differences between samples of bacterial mats taken from the same freshwater lake. For samples taken from the lake on Irizar Island, 227 OTUs are common, and from Uruguay Island – 366 OTUs. Other OTUs are unique in both groups. Analysis of biological diversity showed that the samples do not differ significantly in this parameter among themselves. However, the Simpson index is high for all samples, which indicates the absence of a pronounced dominance of one or more species in the corresponding

ecotopes and, accordingly, a homogeneous distribution of representatives of different species of microorganisms in them.